

Speculation on the Emergence of Tsallis Entropy from a Uniform Distribution

Part 4 Extropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 24, 2025

In Part 1- 3, we argued for a link between Tsallis entropy and a uniform distribution. In fact, in Part 1, we suggested that the Tsallis entropy form follows from a very simple measure of $1-1/N$ (where N is the number of faces of a die) for a sample of one toss which is then generalized to multiple tosses. In such a scenario $1- 1/(N \text{ power } q)$ is the probability that one does not achieve the q guessed numbers in q tosses and so is a measure of uncertainty, so to speak.

In (1), the notion of extropy for a general distribution is discussed within a Tsallis framework. Extropy is written as: $\{N-1 - \text{Sum over } i (1-p_i \text{ power } q)\} / (1-q)$. In short, p_i is replaced with $1-p_i$ and 1 with $N-1$ and $q=1$ leads to $(1-p_i) \ln(1-p_i)$ instead of $p_i \ln(p_i)$. Given that we have linked Tsallis entropy with a uniform distribution, we try to do the same for extropy.

The Uniform Distribution Maximizes Tsallis Entropy if the Only Constraint is Sum over $p_i=1$

Sum over $i p_i=1$ is a basic definition of classical probability and so the statement that the uniform distribution, $p_i = 1/N$ (where N is the number of equally weighted outcomes), maximizes Tsallis entropy (as shown in (1)), where

$$\text{Tsallis entropy} = \{1- \text{Sum over } i p_i \text{ power } q\} / (1-q) \quad ((1))$$

seems to suggest a link between it and the uniform distribution as we have argued in Part I. We argue that it is interesting that the power q appears in ((1)), when the uniform distribution is linear, i.e $p_i=1/N$. From classical probability theory, $p_i \text{ power } q$ represents an AND situation and so ((1)) seems to suggest that in both the physical world and in statistical sampling, one is not restricted to single guesses or one toss of a die sampling. If this is the case, then ((1)) shows that q influences the uncertainty in these multiple guess or multiple try situations even if $p_i=1/N$. In a later section, we give an example of a possible physical scenario involving a probability for a seed to rot in a particular planting (which is probabilistic), but requires on average three successive planting to break down the seed wall (which is also probabilistic, but a different probability from the rotting case. Thus, two parameters are needed to describe such a physical situation, p_i and q .

If this is in fact the case, we argue that the notion of extropy discussed in (1), namely:

$$\{N-1 - \text{Sum over } i (1-p_i \text{ power } q)\} / (1-q) \quad ((2))$$

should also have a simple interpretation within a uniform probability scheme.

Interpretation of Extropy

Extropy is obtained by replacing p_i with $1-p_i$ in the expression for Tsallis entropy and 1 with $N-1$. In Part I, we argued that p_i represents the probability for a certain guessed value to arise, but $1-p_i$ means that this value does not appear. At first this does not seem to represent a physical idea. If one examines ((2)) for a uniform distribution, one has:

N equations of the form $1 - \sum_i (1-p_i)^q$ or

$$1 - \left\{ \frac{N-1}{N} \right\}^q \text{ minus } 1 \text{ (and then multiply by } 1/(1-q)) \text{ ((3))}$$

If one considers singling out a specific number from N together with q AND scenarios, i.e. q tries or guesses/tosses, then:

$\left\{ \frac{N-1}{N} \right\}^q$ represents the number of scenarios without the special number divided by N and

$$1 - \left\{ \frac{N-1}{N} \right\}^q \text{ ((4))}$$

represents the number of scenarios which include the special number one or more times divided by N . For example, if $N=6$, $q=2$, then $1 - \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^2 = 11/36$ where $11 = 5+5+1$, with the first 5 representing the number of cases in which 1 appears in the first toss and not at all in the second, the second 5 represents 1 not appearing in the first toss, but appearing in the second and 1 represents 1 appearing in both tosses. Then:

$$N=6, q=2 \text{ extropy} = - .8333$$

$$N=6, q=3 \text{ extropy} = -.764$$

$$N=6, q=4 \text{ extropy} = -.702 \text{ ((5))}$$

Thus, one sees that the magnitude of extropy decreases with increased tosses, but decreases somewhat slowly. In other words, all cases are linked to the same uniform distribution, but there is an effect of using multiple toss sampling. As a result, there would also be an effect for physical situations (if they exist and the literature seems to indicate they do) in which multiple tries occur before a success. In other words, if there is less of a probability for the $q=4$ case of a special number, say 1, appearing, this does not necessarily mean that that distribution has changed. Rather, the multiple sampling is the cause of the drop in the number. ((5)) seems to suggest that one must be careful in how one measures outcomes. If a physical system has a built-in scheme which involves q tries, i.e. p_i^q , then one needs to be aware that it is not p_i which changes, but the multiple tries which affect measured appearance of a special number (from N).

As we argued in previous notes, the fact that a particle is present with a certain probability does not necessarily mean that this guarantees a successful interaction. Only the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario, with $q=1$, suggests this viewpoint (which in fact appears in numerous physical scenarios and has been carefully measured).

For example, consider planting a seed for which there is a probability of $\frac{1}{2}$ that it rots and $\frac{1}{2}$ that it does not and that on average, one must try planting/replanting it 3 times (perhaps to break down the outer shell). Then the probability that it does not rot and germinates is not $\frac{1}{2}$, but $\frac{1}{8}$. In such a case, each successive planting of the seed has an independent probability of $\frac{1}{2}$ for it to rot, but in the case of germinating, the probability is not really independent because multiple tries are required. If one assumes a breaking down of the seed coat, there is memory in the process, and only the rotting part is random. Furthermore, there are two different probabilities at work, the probability to rot/not rot and a probability to break down the seed coat. This second probability is not explicitly given, but rather an associated average, q is used, which indicates that one is really dealing with two different sets of probabilities.

Thus, $((4))$, added N times for each number in N represents the cumulative sum of probabilities of the numbers in N appearing (not being absent as in the case of entropy). Finally, this number is added to -1 and divided by $1-q$ so that the $q=1$ limit restores:

$(1-p_i) \ln(1-p_i)$ $((5))$ as shown in (1) .

Thus, extropy, in the uniform distribution context and for other probabilities), is a measure of the likelihood for a guess or number to appear in a set of q tries/tosses or guesses and so is in a sense the opposite of entropy. For a distribution other than a uniform one, one has different p_i values and so in a sense averages over them by summing N - \sum over i p_i power q . (Then one adds -1 and divides by $1-q$.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in Part I that the Tsallis entropy expression follows simply from $1-1/N$, $1-1/(NN)$ etc for a uniform distribution, where N is the number of possible outcomes of a die. In other words, one has the notion of taking several successive samples from a uniform distribution by using 1 guess/1 toss, 2 guesses/2 tosses etc. This is represented by the parameter q . One might argue that one may always use $q=1$ which leads to Shannon's entropy (i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann viewpoint). Physically, however, there may be mechanisms which involve p_i power q . In particular, it is possible that the presence of a particle is not sufficient for a successful interaction. It might take q tries at interaction on average for one successful one to occur.

In (1) , the notion of extropy is given which follows from Tsallis entropy with $p_i \rightarrow 1-p_i$ and 1 replaced with $N-1$. Given that we tried to explain the Tsallis entropy form in Part I based on a uniform distribution, we try to give an interpretation of extropy here, also using a uniform distribution. We argue that one essentially has N equal equations: $1- \sum$ over i $(1-p_i)$ power q which are added and then added to -1 before dividing by $1-q$. The main idea, we argue, is in each: $1- \sum$ over i $(1-p_i)$ power q which we interpret to represent the probability that a special number from among N appears at least once in q guesses/tries. One then adds this N times to obtain the total probability for each of the N numbers, (which in the case of the uniform probability is equivalent to multiplying by N , but this is not the case for other distributions).

Finally, adding -1 and dividing by $1-q$ leads to a situation for which $q=1$ yields $(1-p_i)\ln(1-p_i)$. Thus, extropy seems to be a measure for a number to appear, rather than not appear as in the case of entropy.

References

1. Balakrishnan, N. and Buono, F. and Longobari, M. On Tsallis Extropy with an application to pattern recognition 2020 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2103.07168>